

ARTIFICIALLY INTELLIGENT SELF-DRIVEN CAR WITH OBSTACLE AVOIDANCE

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Abstract: This Report is About Artificially Intelligent Self-Driven Car with Obstacle Avoidance. The aim of the Project is to design and create an automated self-Driven car that can also be controlled by desktop application via internet. The car can be controlled from any PC as long as it is connected to an internet connection. A camera will also be used to observe the motion of the car. The user will just set the destination by just clicking on the map, the car will drive itself and will reach to its destination without any human involvement.

Keyword: are missing please Add them

Introduction: This project is about self-driven car that can follow routes via predefined maps provided by the server using GPS device, without any human intervention. It describes independent vehicle benefits and costs, forecasts their likely development and achievements based on experience with previous vehicle technologies, and defines how they will affect developing decisions such as most favourable road, parking and local travel supply. enhanced security, power preservation and pollution decreasing, will only be important when independent vehicles become common and economical, probably in the 2040s to 2060s, and some benefits may require forbidding Human-driven vehicles on self-assured routes, which could take longer. This project is very helpful for everyone. Exponents of model based on independent cars say they would control misfortune caused by human error, all traffic accidents are basically caused by human errors. Furthermore, the prediction of this model can improve traffic flow and can low the traffic jam and erased the errors caused by humans, and can overcome on the expressway capacities other things like transportations around the global village, anything can be done via this effective model capacity prediction.

Corporations designing and developing, trailing Cars with no driver including some of international firms like Audi, BMW, and Volvo. Google is more aware about independent car with no driver can be useful in daily life.

Problem Statement: Self-driven vehicles is able to decrease the ratio of accidents and traffic jam, and can save time by doing something more important than driving. These are satisfaction usually assigned to maintain; as a result, independent vehicles can help for maintaining the ratio of self-driven cars in cities and can ensure security of passengers and durability with efficient level of maintenance.

Methodology:

[1] The User points a destination with the help of mapping tool by showing short distance to passenger or user destination. Special purpose tools calculates a route through Google Direction API and with the help of GPS and Compass and starts the car to go on its way.

Ultrasonic sensors help to avoid the obstacles during the drive. The ultrasonic sensors are placed on car right, left, front, and back and also at Ground to detect earth surface. We are using two Arduino Mega board for controlling the sensors and compass sensors and also a camera for video streaming.

It will be controlled by a desktop application. The logics for navigation system will be implemented in windows application the user will just click on the location where they want to drive the car, and the car will automatically be driven to that place. An override function is available to allow a human to take control of the vehicle. This option will be used for off-road places on the map.

Defect Containment: Software fault tolerance

We need higher levels of reliability, availability, or dependability in this system. Primary software fault tolerance techniques:

Recovery blocks

Use repeated execution of the software of the car
Check local execution faults leads to system failures

N-version programming (NVP), and their variations

We can use N copies of the same program with different versions fulfilling the same requirements of our project

This will check local failures doesn't compromise global execution result.

Defect Containment:

SAFETY ASSURANCE AND FAILURE CONTAINMENT

As this system is safety critical system, our primary concern is the ability to prevent accidents from happening. Accident is a major failure in our case

A little type of failure can lead to an accident that can be major one. We can use hazardous lights when a failure occurs so that other car drivers can save themselves from accidents.

We can also use automatic brakes if any system failure detected.

Expected outcome:

- Reduction in car accidents
Avoid human Errors
- Efficient use of highways.
Two Seconds Rule
- Optimal Speed
Fuel Efficient Drive (save 10-15 % fuel)
Environment Friendly.
- Increases in productivity

Conclusion:

Upon addressing the mechanics of the driverless car as well as its benefits and potential issues, it is quite interesting to see how the world will actually become by the year 2040 to 2060. With the help of Google Maps, Hardware Sensors and Artificial Intelligence, this driverless car will definitely hit the roads and change the whole travelling concepts.

References

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